

The editor's-in-chief address

Dear Reader!

You are holding in your hands the latest issue of the Ukrainian Information Space, a scholarly professional journal on journalism, as well as information, library, and archival affairs. The biennial was founded in the modern Ukrainian era and, as of this issue, has just crossed the boundary of its first five-year anniversary. This is the eleventh issue in the order of publication.

This is the third issue of the UIS, which is created by the mobile editorial team of the founding organisation, KNUKiM, in the context of the full-scale war against Ukraine unleashed by Russia. It is, therefore, understandable why the cruel and unfair war for Ukrainians and the international community is increasingly present in our authors' research. After all, any theory in the humanities is, first of all, a generalised practice of the actual, topical, socially significant. This is especially true in journalism, which, from its inception, was intended to "paint history" truthfully.

So, first of all, I draw attention to publications with the "stamp of war".

Professor Marian Zhytariuk from Lviv was one of the first to study the mission and rank of journalists, photojournalists, cameramen and eyewitness bloggers — all those brave and loyal media professionals who seek to tell the world the truth about Russian aggression. This article can be considered a successful and worthy of emulation attempt not only to rethink the work of the media in the extreme conditions of warfare but also to engrave in the memory of Ukrainians the names of journalists — victims and heroes of the war, to create an initial martyrology of those who died for freedom and democracy in Ukraine.

The article "Destruction of Museum Heritage by the Russian Aggressor in 2022" by Ihor Sklenar, based on media materials, is in line with this theme.

The most resonant examples of damage and destruction of museum heritage objects by the Russian occupiers are analysed through the prism of statistics, articles from print and online publications, and journalistic assessments.

Tetiana Rohova, a researcher from Zaporizhzhia, chose the press of frontline regional centre of Zaporizhzhia as the object of analysis. The questions and answers in this article are quite specific and highly relevant to the activities of the local media: what changes have been made

to the content emphasis, genre forms, video content, lexical norms, journalistic standards, advertising, and commissioned materials? This is not only valuable material from a scientific point of view but also an interesting lecture for students-journalists.

A new, somewhat unexpected research angle was chosen by the young applicant Maryna Otrishko — city murals as a form of informational resistance to Russian aggression. The collected and commented images carry a powerful educational and cognitive charge of informational and artistic murals — a kind of provocative form of influence on the consciousness of citizens through street art.

In addition to the first two thematic sections "Actual Issues of the Ukrainian Information Space" and "Theory and Practice of Journalism" the topic of war and journalism is also present in the section "Publicistics". The publication "Knights of the Truthful Word at KNUKiM" describes the first steps of a new social movement of journalism students at this university. This movement, which supported the nationwide initiative to create a martyrology of the fallen heroes of the recent Russian-Ukrainian war, became known abroad. In Italy, for example, it has led to the awarding of one-off scholarships to journalism students for the best essays in the "Tell the Story of a Fallen Hero" competition. Such essays are systematically published by the editorial board of the all-Ukrainian weekly "Slovo Prosvity".

The review of this block of publications, which is strong in terms of facts and the degree of their comprehension, should be completed with the article by Professor Tetiana Humeniuk "Culture of Memory: The Revolution of Dignity Phenomenon in Contemporary Scientific Reflection". Through the prism of the collective experience of the Maidan of late 2013 — early 2014, the author analyses the cultural, social, and psychological changes in Ukrainian society caused by these and subsequent events and their inseparability from global processes.

Another topic of the issue.

The article by the author of these lines is devoted to the creative aspects of journalism, namely the actual problems of methods and technologies of creating multigenre materials. Like the previous one (about the problems of genre creation), it provokes a professional debate between media theorists and practitioners around the long-standing, but still unfinished, discussion: can writing be taught, or is the profession of journalism for everyone?

With the article by Alina Nalyvaiko, a graduate of the Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts, "Trends in Violation of Professional

Standards in Contemporary Ukrainian Journalism", the journal continues the scientific discussion on this important topic that began in the previous issue. After all, the acuteness and unresolved nature of several problems in this area of media activity is particularly evident in the current dramatic times for our country.

This time, the section "History of Journalism and Book Publishing" is also rich and interesting, in terms of the breadth and depth of its comprehension of the issues. I would like to highlight here the articles by Maiia Nahorniak on the radiotelegraph and radio communication as a strategic task of the UPR and Olena Syniavska on the language policy of the UPR government in the editorial policy of the newspaper "Nova Rada". They contain some important messages for those who are called upon to formulate new content and new priorities for the humanitarian policy of the Ukrainian state in general and the information policy in particular in completely different socio-political circumstances from the previous ones.

The historical issues in the context of its contemporaneity are expanded and emphasised by the skilfully written articles by Oleksandr Halych (on the "Vik" publishing house), Ihor Sribniak and Natalia Sydorenko on the publishing achievements of Ukrainians in exile, Lilia Sylevych (Lviv newspaper "Dilo"), and Mykhailo Koleka on the fate of the eleventh-century Ukrainian book monument, the Reims Gospel.

What topical issues from the past, present, and future of Ukrainian journalism, information, library, and archival affairs will the next issue of our journal cover? To a large extent, the answer to this question will depend on you, dear readers.

Therefore, I invite to cooperation all sympathisers and supporters of the UIS's editorial policy who share its main formula: about Ukrainian journalism studies, as well as journalism itself, in the context of the world – professionally, decently, patriotically.

Mykola Tymoshyk,
Editor-in-Chief
of "Ukrainian Information Space"